

Model analysis of private teachers' innovative work behavior improvement after the COVID-19 pandemic

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ABSTRACT

After the COVID-19 pandemic, educational organizations' learning process experienced significant changes, especially related to innovative work behavior. It is undeniable that building innovative work behavior requires strong self-efficacy and organizational commitment and is supported by conducive workplace happiness. This research aims to analyze models for improving the innovative work behavior of private teachers after the COVID-19 pandemic based on self-efficacy, organizational commitment, and workplace happiness. The research model is oriented towards a quantitative causality approach. Data was collected online using a Google form, and a sample of 100 teachers was obtained. Using a purposive sampling formula, the foundation for sample determination is geared toward a non-probability sampling strategy. Instrument tests, normality tests, regression tests, correlation tests, hypothesis tests, and coefficient of determination were all utilized in data analysis. The results of the study demonstrate that innovative work behavior is highly influenced by workplace happiness, organizational commitment, and self-efficacy. According to the study's conclusions, encouraging creative work behavior requires teachers to have the confidence to do so. Furthermore, the psychological state of educators has a significant impact on their ability to generate novel and creative ideas.

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1. INTRODUCTION

After the COVID-19 pandemic, many changes have occurred in organizational lines, especially in educational organizations [1]. As one of the pillars for advancing education, schools are required to provide the best service for the community. This condition requires high enthusiasm for teachers as the school's main human resource [2]. Schools need to encourage teachers to do all kinds of innovative work [3]. To make the learning environment engaging and productive while also encouraging pupils to participate more actively, a teacher must have innovative ideas [4]. In building an organization, increasing innovation does not depend on ideas or individual contributions alone but is the collaboration of the entire team or organization [5]. Heterogeneous teams will bring many perspectives and new ideas to the innovation process, this is because the team will provide a variety of skills, knowledge, and information sets to understand the problem from various angles that support generating innovative solutions [6]. Related to organizational factors, organization must have a vision, mission, and strategy that teachers can understand [7]. This has the strongest

impact on teacher innovation behavior because strategy sets the direction for teacher activity, such as targets and when they should be achieved. Innovative work behavior is the discovery, experience, and application of ideas, processes, products, and procedures that are new or adopted into organizations that are carried out to benefit work performance, work groups, organizations, and the wider community [8]. An essential component for the business is the presence of creative and innovative activity [9]. Organizational development and performance improvement require innovative work behavior since the ensuing innovations can extend or improve a variety of activities [10]. Teachers who exhibit creative work practices are likely to exceed the organization's average job aim [11]. Additionally, in order to attain innovative work behavior, self-efficacy is required, as the primary responsibility of educators is to foster creativity and generate fresh concepts [12].

Self-efficacy is very important because self-efficacy influences individuals in their work to achieve their goals, including predicting what will happen [13]. Self-efficacy, which is a belief in one's own ability to solve issues, is innate in all people. However, people's beliefs about their own abilities to handle problems vary depending on their experiences and personalities [14]. Teachers' creative self-efficacy is defined by social-cognitive theory as the conviction that they can perform tasks to the best of their ability [15]. Instructor attitude influences learning activities and their capacity to carry them out in the classroom, and instructor self-efficacy might have an impact on this [16]. Individual convictions about their capacity for innovative performance contribute to the organization's best possible goal-achieving. Thus, teaching methods may be impacted by a teacher's degree of self-efficacy. A teacher with high self-efficacy may be more motivated to work hard, whereas a teacher with low self-efficacy may avoid implementing competencies in an effective manner. People who have strong self-efficacy might be more self-assured and motivated to act creatively [17]. In addition, individuals are also involved in work creatively, which ultimately has an impact on work innovation [18]. Self-efficacy can increase individual confidence and self-confidence to add insight and information in completing work [19]. Related to the teacher's task in the classroom, self-efficacy is very important for every teacher because the success of innovative learning methods is very dependent on the individual teacher's beliefs and self-confidence to apply and develop learning [14], [16] found that self-efficacy positively affects innovative work behavior. Consequently, this investigation leads to the formation of the theory based on the findings of several earlier studies:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Self-efficacy influences innovative work behavior. Every organization still needs human resources as part of the organization. However, in becoming part of an organization, teachers need to be trained to commit [20]. Organizational commitment is influenced by instructors' dedication, which is a crucial component of the organization [21]. Organizational commitment is an important behavioral dimension that can be used to assess teachers' propensity to remain members of an organization [17]. An organization needs highly committed teachers to carry out their activities to achieve organizational goals [22]. In increasing the commitment of teachers to be loyal to their organizations. Mohamed and Ruth [23], creating a sense of ownership of the organization by creating a feeling that this organization belongs to every teacher in it is representative of a strong organizational commitment. Each teacher's commitment can be influenced by the teacher's characteristics, including his tenure in the organization, and each employee's different needs and desires [24]. Job characteristics, such as task identity and opportunities to interact with co-workers, can generate new ideas for innovation at work [25]. Teachers with a high level of dedication will strive to work as hard as they can to meet organizational objectives and boost production [26]. As a result, a high level of dedication is crucial for an organization to meet its objectives. The ability to obtain maximum work outcomes through inventive work is one advantage of a teacher's devotion to the organization [26]. Previous studies such as [27], [28] stated that organizational commitment is a crucial and significant factor influencing teachers' innovative work behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic. There is a high correlation between these two features, according to the findings of another study that looked at the link between organizational commitment and creative work behavior [21]. Consequently, this investigation leads to the formation of the theory based on the findings of several earlier studies:

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Organizational commitment influences innovative work behavior. Happiness is defined as well-being, a good outlook, a pleasant mood, and pleasant emotions. Research has shown that these characteristics promote individual engagement and mold behavior in a way that promotes improved organizational performance [29]. Feeling happy at work does not mean endless fun and joy or someone not having a bad day or feeling sad, but the most important thing is that prosperity can create a high (tough) identity that allows a person to recover faster from a downturn [30]. Someone who is in a happy working environment will certainly form a strong mentality to carry out work to the fullest. Happiness at work occurs when teachers feel happy working and perceive their work environment as something pleasant so that work activities are satisfying and enjoyable [31]. Abdullah *et al.* [31] a sense of happiness at work is a set of controlling feelings and thoughts that allow one to maximize performance and achieve innovative work ideas contentment in the workplace has the power to unleash creativity, optimize output, and empower staff

members to fulfill their potential [32]. In other words, if the teacher feels happy, it will create a positive and relaxed work environment that is not stressful. This situation will encourage creativity and innovative behavior at work [33], [34] proves that happy teachers are significantly more productive, have creative ideas and behave innovatively in dealing with various work problems. In the context of classroom learning, if a teacher can spread a sense of happiness to his students, it will create a productive classroom atmosphere, encouraging teachers to make work more innovative. Previous research examining the association between creative work behavior and workplace satisfaction found a strong correlation between the two [35], [27]. Consequently, this investigation leads to the formation of the theory based on the findings of several earlier studies.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Workplace happiness influences innovative work behavior.

2. METHOD

Using a causality quantitative research design technique, quantitative data were gathered for this investigation. This study makes use of a Pematang Siantar City private high school. The study's participants were all permanent instructors at Pematangsiantar City's private high schools who had the status of private teachers. The researchers selected these teachers by sending questionnaires to a total of 100 teachers. Purposive sampling was used to determine the research sample. Regarding the inquiries specified in the digital survey. Instrument tests, normality tests, regression tests, correlation tests, hypothesis tests, and coefficient of determination were all utilized in data analysis. The data analysis tool uses the SPSS version 24 program. Then the operational definitions of the research variables are explained briefly in Table 1.

Table 1. Operational definition of research variables

Variable	Code	Items	Reference
Self-Efficacy	SE1	Task achievement	[36], [15]
	SE2	Problem solving	
	SE3	Job optimization	
Organizational Commitment	OC1	Affective Commitment	[37], [38]
	OC2	Continuance Commitments	
	OC3	Normative Commitments	
Workplace Happiness	WH1	Positive Emotions	[30], [31]
	WH2	Happiness Engagement	
	WH3	Positive Relationships	
	WH4	accomplishments	
	WH5	Workplace Happiness Meaning	
Innovative Work Behavior	IWB1	Generations	[39], [40]
	IWB2	Promotion	
	IWB3	Realization	

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Descriptions of research respondents

The data was gathered using an online survey that was sent to Indonesian private high school instructors via the applications Telegram and WhatsApp, with assistance from Google Form media. Only 100 of the 115 respondents who completed the online questionnaire provided legitimate information, according to the summary of their responses. Table 2 presents a quick summary of further information about the research respondents' characteristics.

3.1.2. Validity and reliability test

It was determined that all study indicators had values over 0.30 and that the measuring items employed in this investigation were valid based on the validity test Table 3. The measurement questions on the questionnaire, which specified the indicators of the variables, were then measured in a reliability experiment. If an individual's response to a questionnaire remains constant or occasionally returns to normal, it might be considered dependable. All indicators have a Cronbach alpha value for each instrument >0.70 , as demonstrated by the reliability trials in Table 4, indicating the dependability of each instrument.

Table 2. Descriptions of research respondents

Categories	Details	Amount	Percentages (%)
Gender	Men	26	26
	Woman	74	74
Age (years)	20-29	10	10
	30-39	23	23
	40-49	40	40
	50-59	27	27
Level of education	D1 to D3	11	11
	Bachelors	70	70
	Masters	19	19
Years of service (years)	<1	8	8
	1-5	22	22
	6-10	25	25
	>10	45	45

Table 3. Validity test results

Variable	Corrected items–Total correlation	N of Items	Test results
Self-Efficacy	0.471	9	Valid
Organizational Commitment	0.489	9	Valid
Workplace Happiness	0.516	15	Valid
Innovative Work Behavior	0.587	9	Valid

Table 4. Reliability test results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items	Test results
Self-Efficacy	0.740	9	Reliable
Organizational Commitment	0.758	9	Reliable
Workplace Happiness	0.890	15	Reliable
Innovative Work Behavior	0.772	9	Reliable

3.1.3. Multiple regression test

Based on the aforementioned multiple linear regression findings, the equation model $v=8.827+0.324X_1+0.257X_2+0.595X_3$ is produced. This suggests that workplace happiness, organizational commitment, and self-efficacy all positively influence creative work behavior. Additionally, it may be understood as follows based on the data analysis (Table 5) results presented in these equations:

- A constant value of 8.827 means that if self-efficacy, organizational commitment, and workplace happiness are considered zero, the value of innovative work behavior will be 6.622.
- The beta coefficient value on the self-efficacy variable is 0.324, which means that every change in the self-efficacy variable by one unit will result in a change in innovative work behavior of 0.324 units assuming the other variables are at a constant value.
- The beta coefficient value on the variable, organizational commitment is 0.257, which means that every change in the organizational commitment variable by one unit will result in a change in innovative work behavior of 0.257 units assuming the other variables are at a constant value.
- The beta coefficient value for the workplace happiness variable is 0.505, which means that every change in the workplace happiness variable by one unit will result in a change in innovative work behavior of 0.505 units assuming the other variables are at a constant value.

Table 5. Multiple regression test results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-count	Sig.
		B	std. Error			
1	(Constant)	8.827	2057		3.820	.000
	Self-efficacy	.324	058	.332	3.510	.000
	Organizational commitment	.257	072	.193	2.240	.028
	Workplace happiness	.505	076	.237	2.801	.003

Note: a is Predictors: (constant), innovative work behavior

3.1.4. Simultaneous and partial hypothesis tests

Experiment F was utilized to investigate the association between variables at the same time. To find out if workplace happiness, organizational commitment, and self-efficacy all influence creative work

behavior at the same time, simultaneous hypothesis testing was done. The F-count value is $86.940 >$ from F-table with $(0.05; 96)$ of 2.47 or with a significance of $0.000 < \alpha < 0.05$, based on the simultaneous test analysis results in Table 6. This suggests that workplace happiness, organizational commitment, and self-efficacy all have a simultaneous and acceptable impact on innovative work behavior. Additionally, a partial testing study was carried out to ascertain how workplace satisfaction, organizational commitment, and self-efficacy relate to characteristics related to innovative work behavior. The t test findings in this study are as follows, based on the data analysis results in Table 4:

- Self-efficacy obtained a significant level of $0.000 \leq \alpha < 0.05$, meaning self-efficacy significantly affects innovative work behavior.
- Organizational commitment obtained a significant level of $0.028 \leq \alpha < 0.05$, meaning that organizational commitment has a significant effect on innovative work behavior.
- Workplace happiness obtained a significant level of $0.003 \leq \alpha < 0.05$, meaning that workplace happiness has a significant effect on innovative work behavior.

Table 6. Simultaneous test results

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	F	Sig.
1 Regression	99.695	3	18.940	.000b
Residual	198.905	96		
Total	296.600	99		

3.1.5. Determination coefficient test

A model's capacity to explain the variance of the dependent variable is gauged by looking at its coefficient of determination. Table 7 provides an explanation of the findings of the study's determination test. Table 7 provides the data analysis results. The coefficient of determination is 0.481, meaning that workplace happiness, organizational commitment, and self-efficacy account for 48.1% of the level of innovative work behavior, while other factors not covered in this study considering for 52.9% of the total.

Table 7. Determination coefficient test results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	std. Error of the Estimate
1	.619a	.481	.470	1.761

Note: a is Predictors: (constant), innovative work behavior

3.2. Discussion

Based on the first H1's findings, it is possible to draw the conclusion that self-efficacy positively and significantly influences innovative work behavior. Innovative methods are typically used by educators with strong creative self-efficacy to fulfill their professional responsibilities. Students gain from teachers with high self-efficacy when those teachers have strong positive self-efficacy [42]. Strong self-efficacy beliefs seem to make teachers more open to experimenting with and eventually using novel teaching techniques. However, while assessing one's own skills, self-efficacy takes into account both one's emotional and physical health. Teachers who have poor self-efficacy perceive stress and tension-related behaviors as indicators of their susceptibility to subpar work [18]. All teachers who believe they are good have a great sense of confidence in themselves. A person with strong self-efficacy is aware of their capabilities and the necessary steps to address issues. In order to overcome uncertainty and failure in the process of innovation, all teachers require positive self-efficacy. Employees who possess the necessary knowledge, abilities, and work environment to foster their creativity might be considered suitably qualified for positions demanding creative thinking. A teacher's creativity might be inspired by aspects of self-efficacy, such as problem-solving skills [12]. Under some conditions, this kind of activity can boost teachers' self-efficacy. Every teacher that believes in their own abilities makes an effort to engage in creative activities and is always inspired to come up with fresh, cutting-edge concepts for the classroom learning process. Having high levels of self-efficacy facilitates instructors' creative development.

Based on the first H2's findings, it can be said that organizational commitment significantly and favorably influences innovative work behavior. These findings demonstrate how crucial it is for there to be organizational commitment within the context of the school organization in order to support teachers' innovative ideas. A teacher that is very committed will like what they do and be able to work with complete accountability. Unlike educators who don't care much about the organization. Each teacher's commitment can be influenced by their characteristics, including their tenure in the organization, as well as the different needs

and desires of each teacher. The level of teacher organizational commitment has long been considered a fundamental element for achieving better performance for companies [41]. A teacher with ongoing commitment finds it difficult to leave his organization because opportunities to gain comfort in work are challenging in other organizations. Job characteristics such as task identity and opportunities to interact with co-workers can generate confidence to produce innovative work ideas [42]. The tendency of individuals to commit themselves to various organizational activities based on the awareness felt by individual employees when they stop or leave in carrying out various organization activities. If the implementation of commitments from the organization is not implemented optimally, then this will impact activities to generate work ideas to be slow [1]. If organizational commitment can be managed properly, this will trigger teachers to work optimally according to their innovation capabilities.

Following the results of the first H3, it can be concluded workplace happiness positive and significant effect on innovative work behavior. These results confirm that aspects of workplace happiness while in the work environment can help teachers create innovative new ideas. Furthermore, a positive work atmosphere and camaraderie among coworkers may foster an environment that is conducive to idea sharing, teamwork, and trying out novel solutions. Teachers are more willing to take chances and adopt novel ways to teaching and learning when they sense that the administration and their fellow educators appreciate and support them. There have been various studies that have made passing references to the connection between happiness and a sense of gratitude. For example [23], [34], have suggested that practicing virtues of character, including gratitude, can promote true happiness. Happiness has used the terms happiness and subjective well-being in the context of the complexity of psychological constructs that significantly affect teachers' self-ability to do innovative work. Furthermore, to create innovative work behavior, you first get happiness in the work itself. In order to boost affective commitment and support lasting and normative commitment, organizations must try to create and preserve a happy work environment. This will help to guarantee that workers' aspirations to develop creative behavior are realized. Naturally, if teachers are able to effectively manage their job-related happiness, particularly with regard to fulfilling their professional responsibilities, this will enable the organization to achieve more optimal work output [31].

4. CONCLUSION

The major finding of the study revealed that there was self-efficacy factor is a foundation for teachers to create innovative ideas when doing work. Teachers with good self-efficacy generally know their abilities so they can easily generate innovative power along with their work. Individuals with strong self-efficacy are often more willing to take chances. Innovation in the area of IWB frequently entails taking chances to explore novel concepts and investigating novel ideas. Self-assurance in one's skills might boost the bravery to attempt new things and confront uncertainty. Consequently, in order to overcome uncertainty and failure during the innovation process, every teacher requires positive self-efficacy. Organizational commitment is a crucial component of the organization's development, in addition to self-efficacy, which the organization must take into account. Innovative work practices cannot be implemented as effectively as possible without a strong organizational commitment from individuals. Teachers must make a strong organizational commitment in order to achieve school goals. The influence of a strong organizational commitment to increasing the effectiveness, efficiency, and productivity of teachers' creative conduct has been felt since the commencement of the initiative. Failure is viewed as a necessary component of learning in innovative societies. The manner in which a company handles failure is indicative of its commitment to IWB. Employees are more inclined to take chances while exploring novel concepts in a company that embraces risk and views failure as a teaching moment. Employee trust is fostered by organizational commitment. Workers are more inclined to act creatively when they believe that their employer encourages them to do so. Teachers with a high level of dedication will strive to work as hard as they can to meet organizational objectives and boost productivity. Perhaps a deeper comprehension of these concepts from many angles and more accurate measurement instruments will contribute to our knowledge of the phenomena of desire and happiness at work.

This further clarifies whether it is uniquely helpful for understanding the individual and its application in human resource development. To create happiness at work, The main mindset human resource (HR) needs to apply to employees is self awareness. Thus, this study provides sufficient insight into using the happiness at work instrument as a valid and reliable measure for measuring innovative work behavior. People are often more driven and passionate at work when they are satisfied in their jobs. These circumstances foster an atmosphere that encourages creativity. Happy workers are more inclined to use their imaginations, take chances, and attempt novel methods to their work. One of the key factors in developing a collaborative work culture is employee happiness. Teams that are at ease and like working together are more likely to exchange ideas, offer constructive criticism, and collaborate to come up with novel solutions. Happiness at work may

also lower turnover rates and boost employee loyalty. Furthermore, efforts to improve communication and collaboration between teachers, administrative staff, and school management can create a more solidary and supportive work environment. This can be done through regular meetings, discussion forums, or online platforms that facilitate interaction and exchange of information. Happy employees tend to stay with a company longer, providing stability and continuity that supports long-term innovation development. So, it can be said that happiness at work creates a strong foundation for innovative work behavior by motivating employees, increasing collaboration, and creating an environment that supports the exploration of new ideas.

The sample size and total number of predictor variables included in this study are its main limitations. Furthermore, because private instructors are the main focus of this study, the findings may only be applicable to that demographic and cannot be directly extended to teachers at public schools or other educational institutions. Second, this research is limited to analyzing teachers' innovative work behavior after the COVID-19 pandemic, so it does not include other factors that might influence teacher innovation in the pre-pandemic period. In addition, because the research subject is innovative behavior, other aspects of teacher performance such as teaching quality or learning effectiveness may not be addressed directly. Third, resources and data availability may be a constraint in this research, especially if access to information about post-pandemic private teacher behavior is limited. In addition, methodological constraints such as issues of reliability and validity of measurement instruments also need to be taken into account in conducting accurate analysis. Finally, changes in the educational context during the pandemic may make it difficult to differentiate between the effects of the crisis situation and other factors influencing teachers' innovative behavior.

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